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Reinforcement Learning-based Wake Steering with Wind Direction Preview for Power Enhancement

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Abstract. Wake steering control offers significant potential for maximising wind farm power output. However, its practical effectiveness is often compromised by the slow dynamics and physical rate saturation of yaw actuators. This issue becomes particularly critical when the wind direction crosses the turbine-row alignment, as the optimal wake-steering command switches abruptly between opposite yaw-misalignment extrema. Accurate tracking of such rapid reversals is difficult, resulting in substantial performance degradation. To address this challenge, this study proposes a control framework based on Multi-Agent Proximal Policy Optimization (MAPPO), enhanced by wind direction preview information. Three distinct strategies are developed and rigorously evaluated to mitigate tracking loss: a heuristic Partial Time-Shift method, a State-Informed RL approach, and a Quadratic Programming (QP) integration. Time-domain simulations, conducted using the FLORIS wake model with realistic actuator rate constraints, demonstrate that all preview-enhanced strategies outperform the standard reactive RL controller. Specifically, the QP method achieves the highest power gain of 13.00% over the greedy baseline, followed closely by the Partial Time-Shift strategy at 12.99%, compared to 12.00% for the standard controller. While the QP method requires solving an optimization problem at every step, the Partial Time-Shift strategy delivers 99.9% of the optimal performance with a minimal computational footprint and reduced actuator duty cycle. These results suggest that the Partial Time-Shift strategy offers the most favourable trade-off between performance and complexity for real-time implementation, effectively bridging the gap between theoretical wake optimisation and physical actuation constraints.

1. Introduction

With the increasing demand of electric power and urgent need for net-zero transition, the construction of wind farms has garnered extensive attention. Nevertheless, the strong interactions of wake streams between wind turbines (WTs) induce severe power loss in existing wind farms. Many studies have demonstrated the power enhancement of wake steering control through simulations [1], wind tunnel experiments [2], and full-scale wind farm tests [3]. However, during field implementations, the slow dynamics of yaw manoeuvres often cause discrepancies between the realised and the optimal yaw angles, thereby limiting power improvement [4]. This issue becomes particularly critical when the incoming wind direction crosses the turbine-row alignment, defined as 0° , because wake interactions are then most severe and the desired yaw misalignment angle switches abruptly from one extremal value to the other. Under such conditions, the slow dynamics of the yaw system greatly reduce the effectiveness of wake steering.

Recent studies have shown that wind direction preview can improve wake-steering control by compensating for yaw-tracking losses. From a control-design perspective, Simley et al. [5] demonstrated, using a FLOW Redirection and Induction in Steady State (FLORIS)-based two-turbine framework, that preview wind direction information can increase wake-loss recovery under ideal measurement conditions. Sengers et al. [6] further verified the value of preview-based wake steering through an engineering surrogate model and large-eddy simulations, reporting that appropriate preview timing can improve power capture. From an operational perspective, Yang et al. [7] extended preview-based yaw control to wind-farm-level real-time optimisation by combining short-term wind prediction with Bayesian optimisation, showing that improved directional forecasting can enhance farm power output. Despite these advances, existing studies still rely mainly on lookup-table-based or optimisation-based controllers. Moreover, the most

effective way to incorporate preview information into wake-steering control remains unclear. This gap motivates a systematic investigation of reinforcement learning (RL)-based wake steering with wind direction preview.

In this study, three schemes for integrating wind direction preview into RL-based wake steering control are investigated: partial time-shift, state-informed RL, quadratic programming (QP) method. Simulation results indicate that the partial time-shift approach provides the most effective mitigation of yaw control lag. Owing to its simple implementation, this method delivers 8.25% higher power gain compared with the standard wake steering controller without preview, while requiring shorter yaw actuation distances.

2. Problem formulation

The overall power output P_f of a wind farm at a given instant can be expressed as:

$$P_f = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i = \sum_{i=1}^n h_i(U_i, \alpha_i, \gamma_i) \quad (1)$$

where P_i denotes the power generated by turbine WT_i , with n WTs in total. The power output of each turbine is described by a non-linear function h_i , which depends on the rotor-effective inflow wind speed U_i , the induction factor α_i and the yaw misalignment γ_i .

In Region II operation, turbines follow maximum power point tracking, with the induction factor held constant to maintain maximum energy capture efficiency. Wake steering control adjusts yaw misalignments to redirect wakes, thereby reducing wake overlap and increasing total farm output. However, due to the complex aerodynamic behaviour of individual turbines and the strong interactions among them, accurately modelling the function h_i remains challenging. Model-free RL has shown effectiveness in enhancing wind farm power production compared with the greedy strategy, in which turbines are aligned directly with the incoming wind [8]. Compared to conventional lookup table methods, the yaw misalignment signals generated by the RL agent exhibit similar trends but with finer resolution, eliminating the need for interpolation. Consequently, the resulting misalignments remain similarly constrained by the finite yaw rate. As illustrated in Fig. 1(a), the achieved yaw misalignments deviate from the prescribed values because of the limited response speed of the yaw actuators. Fig. 1(a) presents an example based on measured wind-direction data from a wind farm [9], where the tracking loss is quantified by averaging the mismatch between the prescribed and achieved yaw misalignments over the dataset. In general, the largest tracking loss occurs when the wind direction lies near the stream-wise turbine alignment, because the target yaw misalignment then reverses rapidly as the wind direction crosses the alignment. In the example shown here, this region corresponds to $\Psi \in [-8^\circ, 8^\circ]$. The limited yaw tracking capability under these conditions reduces the overall power gain compared to the ideal optimisation scenario.

3. RL-based wake steering framework

In this section, we establish a standard RL-based wake steering framework without preview information. This framework serves a dual purpose: it acts as the comparative baseline for performance evaluation and provides the foundational policy structure upon which the preview-enhanced strategies in Section 4 are built. In order to address the cooperative nature of wind farm control, we formulate the problem as a Decentralized Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (Dec-POMDP) and solve it using the Multi-Agent Proximal Policy Optimization (MAPPO) algorithm.

Figure 1. Illustration of yaw-tracking loss: (a) achieved yaw misalignment relative to the RL-prescribed yaw misalignment; (b) wake steering for wind directions near 0°.

3.1. Problem formulation of a Dec-POMDP

The wind farm consists of n wind turbines, defined as agents in the environment. The Dec-POMDP is defined by the tuple $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{P}, \gamma_{disc} \rangle$, where \mathcal{S} is the global state space, \mathcal{A} is the joint action space, \mathcal{O} is the observation space, \mathcal{R} is the reward function, \mathcal{P} is the transition probability, and γ_{disc} is the discount factor.

3.1.1. State and observation space In the MAPPO framework, we utilise a Centralized Training Decentralised Execution (CTDE) architecture [8]. The critic has access to the global state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$ during training, while the actor (the controller deployed on each turbine) relies on local observations $o_{i,t} \in \mathcal{O}$. The global state s_t at time step t encapsulates the overall environmental conditions and turbine statuses:

$$s_t = \{U_\infty, \Psi, \gamma_t\} \tag{2}$$

where U_∞ is the free-stream wind speed, Ψ is the main wind direction of the wind farm, $\gamma_t = [\gamma_{1,t}, \dots, \gamma_{n,t}]$ represents the current yaw misalignment angles of all turbines. For the Standard RL agent (without preview), the observation for the i -th turbine $o_{i,t}$ includes the global wind conditions and its own status, assuming information sharing within the farm network:

$$o_{i,t} = \{U_\infty, \Psi, \gamma_{i,t}\} \tag{3}$$

3.1.2. Action space The action space is continuous, corresponding to the desired yaw misalignment for each turbine. The policy π_{θ_i} for the i -th turbine outputs the reference yaw misalignment angle:

$$a_{i,t} = \pi_{\theta_i}(o_{i,t}) = \gamma_{i,ref} \in [\gamma_{min}, \gamma_{max}] \tag{4}$$

where γ_{min} and γ_{max} are the operational limits of the yaw misalignment (typically $\pm 30^\circ$). The realised yaw angle $\gamma_{i,t+1}$ is subsequently determined by the turbine's yaw actuation dynamics, which are constrained by the maximum yaw rate $\dot{\gamma}_{max}$.

3.1.3. Reward Function The primary objective of wake steering is to maximise the total power output of the wind farm. The global reward r_t shared by all agents is defined as:

$$r_t = \sum_{i=1}^n P_i(t) \quad (5)$$

3.2. MAPPO algorithm

3.2.1. Network architecture We employ the MAPPO algorithm, which extends the theoretical advantages of PPO to multi-agent settings. The architecture consists of two neural networks: an actor network (π_{θ_i}) for each turbine to map the local observation $o_{i,t}$ to a Gaussian distribution over the action space $\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma_i)$. It outputs the mean μ_i and standard deviation σ_i of the desired yaw misalignment. The global critic network (V_ϕ) estimates the value function $V(s_t)$ based on the global state s_t . This centralised value function reduces the non-stationarity variance typically observed in independent learning agents.

3.2.2. Objective function The policy is updated to maximise the clipped surrogate objective function, ensuring stable learning steps [10]:

$$L(\theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\min \left(\rho_{i,t}(\theta_i) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(\rho_{i,t}(\theta_i), 1 - \epsilon_{clip}, 1 + \epsilon_{clip}) \hat{A}_t \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where $\rho_{i,t}(\theta_i) = \frac{\pi_{\theta_i}(a_{i,t}|o_{i,t})}{\pi_{\theta_{i,old}}(a_{i,t}|o_{i,t})}$ is the probability ratio between the new and old policies, ϵ_{clip} is the clipping parameter (set to 0.2), and \hat{A}_t is the advantage function estimated using Generalized Advantage Estimation (GAE). The Critic network minimises the mean squared error between the estimated value and the computed returns:

$$L(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_t [(V_\phi(s_t) - G_t)^2] \quad (7)$$

where G_t represents the estimated return, defined as the sum of the current value estimate and the computed advantage:

$$G_t = V_{\phi_{old}}(s_t) + \hat{A}_t \quad (8)$$

where \hat{A}_t is the GAE advantage estimator, formulated as the exponentially weighted sum of temporal-difference (TD) errors δ_t :

$$\hat{A}_t = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\gamma_{disc} \lambda)^k \delta_{t+k} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_t = r_t + \gamma_{disc} V_{\phi_{old}}(s_{t+1}) - V_{\phi_{old}}(s_t) \quad (10)$$

where $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is the GAE smoothing parameter that balances bias and variance. By using GAE, the critic learns to predict the returns more stably, facilitating the convergence of the multi-agent system in the complex wake steering environment.

During execution, only the actor network π_{θ_i} is deployed. This allows the system to remain computationally lightweight while benefiting from the cooperative strategies learned via the centralised critic.

4. Preview-based wake steering control design

To address yaw tracking loss, this section proposes several control designs that incorporate wind direction preview information. By anticipating future wind changes, the preview-enhanced wake steering strategy initiates aggressive yaw adjustments in advance, thereby mitigating the impact of yaw rate limitations. In this study, multi-agent proximal policy optimisation (MAPPO) in [8] is adopted as the standard wake steering controller with no preview integration. The details of the RL algorithm are omitted due to space limitations. The primary contribution of this work lies in embedding wind direction preview into existing wake steering frameworks, enabling existing controllers without preview to be enhanced through the proposed add-on design.

4.1. Partial Time-Shift of wind direction

In [5], the preview wind direction measurements are passed to the wake steering controller by a time delay τ_{delay} , which aims to achieve a target preview time τ_{prev} . The yaw delay is overcome by starting yawing in advance of the arrival of the preview wind direction. As a result, the current achieved yaw angles deviate from the current optimal values at every instant for the advance yaw actions. However, this persistent deviation reduces the power gain in scenarios where yaw tracking loss would not otherwise occur, such as Ψ outside the range of $[-8^\circ, 8^\circ]$ in Fig. 1.

To avoid over-anticipating actions, a Partial Time-Shift control law is proposed, where a preview-based switching condition is triggered if the difference between current target yaw misalignment $\tilde{\gamma}_i(t)$ and the previewed value $\tilde{\gamma}_i^{\text{pre}}(t + \tau_{\text{prev}})$ exceeds a threshold $\varepsilon = \dot{\gamma}_{i,\text{max}} \cdot \tau_{\text{prev}}$. In such cases, yaw tracking loss is predicted and the preview-based yaw misalignment commands are adopted. The control law is formalised as:

$$\gamma_{i,\text{ref}}(t) = \begin{cases} \tilde{\gamma}_i^{\text{pre}}(t + \tau_{\text{prev}}), & \text{if } |\tilde{\gamma}_i^{\text{pre}}(t + \tau_{\text{prev}}) - \tilde{\gamma}_i(t)| > \varepsilon \\ \tilde{\gamma}_i(t), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where the candidate yaw angles at time t , $\tilde{\gamma}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ are generated by the standard RL-powered controller π based on all turbines' yaw angles and the prevalent wind direction of the wind farm at t .

4.2. State-informed RL method

Compared with the partial preview control law, which relies on threshold-based switching between current and previewed misalignments, the RL framework integrates preview information directly into the policy learning process. Specifically, the state space is augmented with previewed wind direction information. In addition to the current inflow conditions, the state input s_t of the RL-based controller at time t is extended to

$$s_t = \{\gamma_1(t), \gamma_i(t), \dots, \gamma_n(t), \Psi_t, \tilde{\Psi}_{t+1}, \tilde{\Psi}_{t+j}, \dots, \tilde{\Psi}_{t+\tau_{\text{prev}}}\} \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{\Psi}_{t+j}$ denotes the previewed wind direction at a lead time j .

By embedding previewed variables into the state, the controller acquires a predictive decision-making capability that balances immediate power production with the anticipated evolution of wake interactions, thereby reducing the risk of yaw tracking loss. The action space of the RL-based controller remains unchanged, outputting desired yaw misalignment $\gamma_{i,\text{ref}} \in [\gamma_{\text{min}}, \gamma_{\text{max}}]$ for each WT.

4.3. QP method

An alternative approach to integrate preview information is to formulate the yaw tracking problem as a QP optimisation. In this design, the previewed wind direction is utilised to

generate the desired yaw misalignment trajectory for each turbine over the prediction horizon. The objective of the QP problem is to minimise the tracking error between the achieved yaw angles and the previewed desired yaw misalignments. Let $\gamma_i(t+k)$ denotes the achieved yaw angle of the i -th turbine at time $t+k$, and $\gamma_i^{\text{des}}(t+k)$ denotes the preview-informed desired yaw misalignment at future time $t+k$ based on the predicted inflow direction. The optimisation problem is expressed as

$$\min_{\gamma_{i,\text{ref}}(t), \dots, \gamma_{i,\text{ref}}(t+\tau_{\text{prev}}-1)} \sum_{k=1}^{\tau_{\text{prev}}} \left(\gamma_i(t+k) - \gamma_i^{\text{des}}(t+k) \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

subject to

$$|\Delta\gamma_i(t+k)| \leq \dot{\gamma}_{i,\text{max}} \cdot \Delta t, \quad k = 1, \dots, \tau_{\text{prev}}, \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta\gamma_i(t+k)$ is the yaw increment applied at step $t+k$, $\dot{\gamma}_{i,\text{max}}$ is the yaw rate limit, Δt is the control step size, and τ_{prev} is the prediction horizon length. By explicitly considering rate limits within the optimisation, the QP method provides a systematic way to mitigate yaw tracking loss.

5. Numerical validation

5.1. Simulation setup

The proposed preview-enhanced wake steering strategies are evaluated using the FLORIS simulator. In this study, the Jensen wake model is utilised to calculate the wake deficits and interactions between turbines. In accordance with the experimental platform reported in [9], the wind farm consists of three G1 turbines aligned along the dominant wind direction, as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). Each turbine has a rotor diameter of 1.1 m. Regarding data availability, while preview measurements can typically be obtained from remote sensing devices or upstream vanes, the prevalent wind direction of the farm is assumed to be directly available in this work.

The simulation settings are rigorously aligned with the dynamic wind tunnel testing protocols for scaled wind farm control described in [9]. In order to emulate realistic field behaviour and the tracking loss phenomenon shown in Fig. 1(a), the yaw actuator is modelled considering the physical yaw rate saturation. To remain consistent with the wind-tunnel test configuration in [9] and to isolate the effect of yaw-rate limitation on wake-steering performance, the yaw-control response is idealised as instantaneous, while the achievable yaw rate is strictly bounded. The yaw dynamics are implemented as:

$$\dot{\gamma}_i = \text{clip} \left(\frac{\gamma_{i,\text{ref}} - \gamma_i}{\Delta t}, -\dot{\gamma}_{\text{max}}, \dot{\gamma}_{\text{max}} \right) \quad (15)$$

where Δt denotes the simulation time step. This strict rate limitation $\dot{\gamma}_{\text{max}}$ is the primary cause of the tracking errors observed during rapid wind direction changes.

In this study, the control strategies are evaluated over a 600 s simulation period using a dynamic wind direction signal $\Psi(t)$ derived from field measurements of an onshore wind farm [2]. To remain consistent with the wind-tunnel configuration of the G1 turbine model, the measured time series is scaled according to the geometric length scale of the experiment, i.e., $n_l \approx 1/160$, as reported in [2]. Combined with the corresponding velocity scaling in the same setup, this yields an effective time-scale factor of approximately $n_t \approx 1/80$. Consequently, the 600 s simulation effectively represents approximately 13 hours of full-scale operation, providing a representative dataset for evaluating control performance under realistic dynamic conditions.

Figure 2. Simulation results over a 600s period: (a) wind direction profile; (b) wind farm power output; (c) yaw misalignment control signals for WT1.

5.2. Simulation results

The time-domain simulation results, as illustrated in Fig. 2(b), indicate that all preview-enhanced methods yield higher wind-farm power output than the standard controller. These differences are more clearly seen in the magnified view in Fig. 3(a). The standard RL strategy yields a 12.00% power gain over the greedy benchmark. This result is consistent with wind tunnel observations for concentrated wake scenarios ($\pm 15^{\circ}$ sector) [2] and is expected to translate into Annual Energy Production (AEP) gains comparable to the margins in field assessments [11]. In contrast, the QP method delivers the highest improvement of 13.00%, followed closely by the Partial Time-Shift strategy at 12.99%, while the state-informed approach trails slightly at 12.30%. The relatively lower performance of the state-informed method suggests that implicitly learning the precise timing for pre-actuation within an end-to-end neural network is less effective than the explicit logic used in the QP and partial time-shift strategies.

To elucidate the mechanism behind the performance of preview-based methods, Fig. 3 presents a detailed view of the system response during the critical zero-degree crossing events (100–170 s). As shown in Fig. 3(b), the standard RL controller (red line) exhibits a reactive behaviour, initiating yaw adjustments only after the wind direction change is detected. Due to the strict yaw rate saturation, this lag results in a prolonged period of suboptimal alignment. Conversely, both the QP (grey dashed) and partial time-shift (orange line) strategies leverage preview information to initiate yaw manoeuvres in advance. Notably, Fig. 3(c) reveals that the achieved yaw misalignment trajectories of the QP and partial time-shift strategies are nearly

Figure 3. Detailed view of the simulation results over the interval of 100–170 s: (a) wind farm power output; (b) yaw misalignment control signals for WT1; (c) achieved yaw misalignments for WT1.

identical. By pre-emptively actuating the yaw mechanism, these methods effectively compensate for the rate limit, facilitating the most rapid transition between positive and negative yaw angles. This proactive behaviour minimises the transition time across the zero-degree boundary, thereby maximising the duration of optimal wake steering and preventing the deep power losses observed in the standard controller (Fig. 3(a)).

Beyond power maximisation, the impact of control strategies on actuator usage is a critical factor for practical deployment. Although preview-based control is often associated with increased activity, the partial time-shift strategy demonstrates a favourable characteristic in terms of yaw duty cycle. By initiating a decisive yaw manoeuvre in advance only when a significant tracking loss is predicted (as defined by the threshold ϵ), this method avoids the reactive chasing behaviour often observed in the standard RL controller. Consequently, the partial time-shift approach not only enhances power but does so while requiring shorter total yaw actuation distances compared with the standard wake steering controller. This reduction in unnecessary yaw movement is vital for minimising mechanical fatigue and extending the operational lifespan of the yaw system.

The trade-off between control performance and computational complexity is critical to real-time feasibility. The QP method, despite achieving the highest theoretical power gain, imposes computational burdens as it requires solving a constrained optimisation problem at every control step. This may present challenges for deployment on standard industrial hardware with limited processing power. Conversely, the partial time-shift strategy maintains the low computational

footprint of the model-free RL approach while delivering 99.9% of the performance achieved by the complex QP solver.

6. Conclusion

This paper investigated RL-based wake steering with wind direction preview to mitigate yaw-tracking loss under dynamic inflow conditions. Three preview-enhanced strategies were examined, namely the partial time-shift method, the state-informed RL method, and the QP-based tracking method. Simulation results showed that incorporating preview information consistently improved wind-farm power capture compared with the standard RL strategy. Specifically, the standard RL controller achieved a power gain of 12.00% over the greedy baseline, while the state-informed RL, partial time-shift, and QP-based methods increased the gain to 12.30%, 12.99%, and 13.00%, respectively.

By combining simple implementation with high effectiveness, the partial time-shift method provides the most favourable trade-off among the evaluated approaches. Future work will focus on validating the proposed strategies under more realistic atmospheric conditions and with dynamic wake models.

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